

Internationalisation in education: Assessing English as a foreign language (EFL) teacher education curriculum

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Abstract

The current research investigates how international-mindedness is represented in the Egyptian teacher education (TE) curriculum as a core concept in international education. I adopted qualitative methodology, with thematic analysis being the method of data analysis. I conducted a document analysis of preservice English teacher education curricula using international-mindedness (IM) as a framework. The analysis included internal bylaws of the Faculty of Education, Assiut University, Egypt. Findings suggest that English teacher education curricula did not include references/indications to IM competencies excluding some implicit indications. Conclusions and recommendations highlight the need for curricular changes in the curricula to reflect better/represent IM.

Keywords: *International Education; Qualitative Research; Teacher Education; Document Analysis; Educational Reform.*

JEL Classification: I21; I23; Z13.

1. Introduction

Teacher education (TE) is essential for equipping preservice teachers with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes for their professional roles. It aims to provide teachers with the competencies demanded by the evolving educational landscape. This landscape is marked by diversified educational environment (Manning et al, 2010), constant interconnectedness and globalisation (Trisnawati et al, 2025), and information and communication technology (Fraser, 2023). These changes in the educational landscape are reflected in the Egyptian context where the educational environment is getting evolving and changing as well with the increase of migrants mainly from Africa, lending the educational environment diverse and evolving (Abdel Aziz, 2017). In Egypt, teacher education requires development due to trends in globalisation (Marginson, 2022; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2009), the internationalisation of HE (Ge, 2022), and a globalised school context (Benade, 2017) marked by intercultural and multicultural understanding (Parmigiani et al., 2022) and global awareness (Cuccurullo & Cinganotto, 2020; Lourenço, 2018).

The research examines how IM, namely an openness and curiosity about the world (Singh & Qi, 2013), is reflected in the EFL teacher education curriculum, specifically at the Faculty of Education, Assiut University, Egypt. It suggests that EFL teacher education in Egypt should be improved to better prepare preservice teachers (PSTs) for international educational contexts. Therefore, it aims to address the research question: How is IM represented in the EFL teacher education curriculum, by conducting a document analysis of the TE curriculum documents at the Faculty of Education, Assiut University. This study argues that Egyptian teacher education is not preparing teachers with the competencies needed to be globally employable (El-Halawany, 2018). The research examines how IM is reflected in the EFL teacher education curriculum. The focus of this research on the curricula stems from the fact that teacher education curriculum plays a key role in educating teachers and their future teaching practices and performance (Pountney & Swift, 2024) and they are widely recognised as essential for teachers' professional development and growth (Asim, 2024).

The importance of study stems from the following considerations: First, the theoretical significance lies in developing a conceptual framework. This framework is grounded in the literature, and it is based on Metli and Lane's (2020) conceptualisation of IM, incorporating the two dimensions of global engagement and intercultural competence. Based on these two dimensions of IM, I defined certain teaching practices that could be incorporated into TE curriculum and into teaching practice later. This framework could be further applied to other educational contexts such as

Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education for instance and reconceptualising teacher education in the context of international education. The conceptual framework can be used as a developmental framework of a set of competencies that teacher education practitioners can use. Teacher education curriculum developers can also integrate and adapt these competencies to their specific contexts within the curriculum and stress them in their practices of teacher education. The practical significance includes improving teacher education in the light of international education to keep abreast with the updated knowledge in international education contexts and shifting the focus of curriculum developers to consider international features.

2. Literature Review

The current study is based on the philosophy of international education, and it is originally contextualised within international schools with reference to international-mindedness as a core concept embedded in the educational philosophy and practice of international schools. IM is a key concept that underpins the current study in the context of international education. Understanding this concept is particularly important nowadays as there is a surge towards internationalisation and international education (Hébert & Abdi, 2013; Wolf et al, 2023; Zhang & Cao, 2024).

International-mindedness: Origins and Definitions

International-mindedness is one concept that often resonates throughout literature pertinent to education, especially in international education. It is defined as a complex multi-faceted concept that features a way of thinking, being and acting characterised by an openness to the world and a recognition of our deep interconnectedness to others (International Baccalaureate, 2017). IM has been explored recently in extensive educational literature (Dewey, 2017; Jurasaitė-O'Keefe, 2022; Metli et al, 2018). Originally, IM is a call for peaceful coexistence, as indicated by Mead (1929, cited in Cause, 2012), who argued that IM developed after the first world war (WWI) was perceived as a political concept where the history of the phrase, as Dewey (2017) clarified goes back at least as far as 1929. In educational contexts, it was hoped that there should be an educational philosophy aiming at developing global citizens and preparing children for the challenges of globalisation would achieve such goals.

As globalisation intensifies, the need for IM grows to facilitate global communication. Metli and Lane (2020) emphasise that the increasingly interconnected, globalised, and multicultural world offers more opportunities for communication across cultures. The defining features of IM, such as global and intercultural competence, as identified by Cause (2012) and Singh and Qi (2013), underscore that IM is foundational for international and intercultural human dialogue in contemporary educational landscapes. The increasing trend of globalisation of the world underlines the need for international-mindedness to facilitate global communication. As Metli and Lane (2020) note, a more interconnected and multicultural world offers opportunities for cross-cultural interaction between different individuals.

IM is a concept that often resonates throughout educational literature, particularly international education (e.g., Jurasaitė-O'Keefe, 2022). IM brings into mind a set of mindsets or dispositions that an educational stakeholder should adopt to be described as internationally minded (Bhavnani, 2013). IM can be viewed as a key by-product of international education, or at least a concept that is linked in one way or another to international education. Additionally, Hill (2012) adopts a pragmatic view, defining IM as the application of knowledge and skills to enhance the world through empathy, compassion, and openness to diverse perspectives. Barrett Hacking et al (2016) also emphasise IM as a continuing pursuit influenced by time, space, and interpersonal interactions.

Educational applications of international-mindedness

IM is positioned within international education, which promotes an attitude described as IM (Wells, 2011). Scholars have examined IM in the context of international education. Beek (2019) argues that the desire for international-mindedness reflects an approach to life that embraces differences and fosters collaboration for the greater good through intercultural respect. Practical studies have shown connections between international education and IM. For example, Budrow (2021) explored the experiences of three Canadian teachers starting their careers in international schools worldwide. The findings suggest that some aspects of IM are easily understood and practiced by these teachers, while others require more awareness and effort. Barret Hacking et al (2016) also argue that becoming internationally minded is an ongoing process shaped by time, space, and the people encountered. Additionally, Lai et al. (2014) examined IM in the IB Diploma Programme in Hong Kong and identified challenges teachers face in implementing IM.

Adopting IM is increasingly recognised as important in educational contexts. Zhang (2024) notes that IM has indeed gained popularity due to the proliferation of international education, international schools and curricula. It benefits international students, who Bista (2016) defines as those students moving abroad for HE pursuits. In educational contexts, educators aim at fostering IM to help students become global citizens (see Barratt Hacking & Taylor, 2020). The need for culturally relevant and internationally sensitive university courses reveals the recognition that HE should prepare students for an interconnected diverse world. In this regard, IM promotes interest in human beings, openness to different cultures, and respect for cultural differences (VanAlistine & Holmes, 2016).

The conceptual framework of this study comprises two dimensions: global competence/engagement and intercultural competence, with four competencies applicable to teacher education. First, global competence emphasises integrating global issues/themes and cultures into teaching, as highlighted by Nopas and Kerdsomboon (2024). Kerkhoff and Cloud (2020) also stress the importance of training teachers to teach (about) global competence, while Letot (2023) advocates for global learning to help prepare individuals for a global workforce. Parkhouse and Tichnor-Wagner (2019), on the other hand, link global competence to nurturing diversity in classrooms.

Analysing global resources to advance inclusive school cultures, cultural exchange, and inclusion is the second dimension (Kim et al, 2023; Ainscow, 2024). In order to overcome prejudices and relate cultural knowledge to teaching, intercultural competency starts with critically analysing one's own culture through self-reflection (Cushner & Mahon, 2009; Eden et al., 2024; Hongboontri & Keawkhong, 2014; Lindquist, 2016). Recommendations to internationalise teacher education through cross-cultural content, professional development, experiential learning, and international partnerships suggest that reflective engagement with global educational systems can further improve teachers' pedagogical skills and knowledge (Nopas & Kerdsomboon, 2024; Darling-Hammond, 2017).

International-mindedness and teacher education curriculum

Curriculum is a crucial component of an educational system. Richards (2013) defines a foreign language curriculum as one that plans goals, content, and sequence to align with learners' needs, context, and desired outcomes such as cultural awareness or communicative competence. International-mindedness can play a role in teacher education curriculum, especially for English language teachers. Understanding IM in education is complex and context-dependent, as it is influenced by cultural contexts and teacher readiness (VanAlistine & Holmes, 2016) and as such TE curricula should promote cultural sensitivity to prepare teachers for diverse classrooms, reflecting the ongoing trend of globalisation. Developing IM involves integrating it into curricular, co-curricular, and extracurricular activities (Metli, 2021). Specifically, curricula can nurture IM by fostering a global perspective, embedding intercultural competencies, and promoting positive attitudes toward cross-cultural communication.

3. Methodology

The study adopted a qualitative methodology based on document analysis. Qualitative methodology is appropriate for the current research as it enabled me as a researcher to conduct in-depth analysis and gain rich insights into the phenomenon under investigation. With its focus on the quality of the data rather than quantity, qualitative methodology allowed me to delve into the current complex context, investigating its details and peculiarities thoroughly. Agius (2013) underscores the rich tradition in qualitative research in the study of human social behaviour and cultures, with its purpose being to nurture principles that assist us to apprehend social phenomena in any place possible to advantage an information of the experiences, individuals' perceptions and/or behaviours, and the meanings connected to them.

Qualitative Document Analysis

I used document analysis to analyse teacher education curriculum documents. Morgan (2022) mentions that document analysis has been an underused approach to conducting qualitative research. It can be valuable for many reasons such as when analysing pre-existing texts as it allows researchers to conduct studies, they might not be able to complete otherwise. Document analysis is a systematic research method for reviewing printed and electronic documents and it is valuable in educational research (Bowen, 2009). As a qualitative research method, document analysis encompasses a systematic process of identifying, selecting, interpreting, and integrating information from documents to review and assess their content meaningfully (Kutsyuruba, 2023). In the current study, document analysis helped in understanding the representation of IM practices within the current context which I could not achieve if used other

methods such as interviews as my purpose was to examine the language of the documents. Table 1 below illustrates the data analysed and which documents they were obtained from:

Table 1. Teacher education curriculum document analysis.

Document	Data	Source
Assiut University Website	Mission, Vision, Goals, and strategic objectives	Available online for the public
Faculty of Education website	Mission & Vision	Available online for the public
Department of Curriculum & Teaching Methods website	Overview & Department Goal	Available online for the public
English Language Teacher Education (ELTE) Curriculum – Primary School Teacher	Mission, vision, graduate preservice teacher profile, teacher's knowledge, teacher's skillsets	Document available for staff members (not publicly accessible) (no. of pages = 17)
ELTE Curriculum – Secondary School Teacher	Mission, vision, graduate preservice teacher profile, teacher's knowledge, teacher's skillsets	Document available for staff members (not publicly accessible) (no. of pages = 17)

Source: Developed by the author.

Sampling

Sampling technique was purposive in which the points of analysis are selected according to the research purpose deliberately and hence the name deliberate or judgemental sampling (Bhardwaj, 2019). Bhardwaj also discusses advantages of purposive sampling that there will be no hurdles and thus selecting the sample becomes convenient. Purposive sampling was the method employed, which means that documents were specifically selected according to their applicability to the study's goal (Bhardwaj, 2019). This method made it simpler to choose important documents and obtain insightful information.

According to Morgan (2022), the research questions served as a guide rather than a fixed number of documents. From the university level down to the faculty and department levels, I concentrated on documents pertaining to EFL teacher education. Only the documents indicated in Table 1 were accessible due to access restrictions. As recommended by Plakoyiannaki et al (2023), I used source criticism to support the selection, which entails assessing the documents' reliability and place of origin critically. As Fischer also noted, this methodical approach helps guarantee that the data used is trustworthy and pertinent. I was restricted in what I could analyse of the documents since the above-mentioned sources in Table 1 are the available sources to the best of my knowledge and no other documents could be obtained due to access issues and restrictions.

Context

The research was conducted in the Egyptian higher education (HE) context. This context is evolving since the HE environment in Egypt is more leaning towards engagement with world contexts (i.e., internationalisation) from a Global South example country/state. The state is taking steady steps towards internationalisation of HE (Mediterranean Countries Towards Internationalisation at Home, 2023), adopting a global lens towards education and HE. This context provides a rich environment that can provide opportunities for both theory-and-practice contributions in the field of teacher and HE (British Council, 2023). The research is also conducted at Assiut University which is an Upper Egyptian HE provider. It has some features that make a promising context for conducting qualitative research such as the current research such as embodying sociocultural features distinguishing this area. I also selected this university because of logistical facilities that might not be available elsewhere.

Thematic Analysis

The analysis was thematic (Naeem et al, 2023) and deductive (Fife & Gossner, 2024): it was driven deductively by the conceptual framework adopted in the current study. Braun and Clarke (2006) define thematic analysis as a qualitative analytical method that can be theory-driven (deductive) or independent of theory (inductive), highlighting that one of its benefits is the flexibility in conducting analyses. Through its theoretical freedom, thematic analysis provides a flexible and useful research technique, which can possibly provide a rich and detailed, yet complex data analysis. I used the conceptual framework of international-mindedness as outlined in Figure 1 below for analytical purposes because this specifically designed framework includes key notions and elements of international-mindedness as outlined in the literature (e.g., Singh & Qi, 2013), thus I adopted deductive analytical technique depending on this framework. Therefore, every section of the teacher education curriculum was assessed against this conceptual framework. The hierarchical ascending progress I adopted to the analysis by approaching the documents from the highest level of the educational spectrum as university through to the end of the structure at programme levels allowed a thorough informed understanding of whether international-mindedness was ever reflected in those documents and, if any, in what form (see Cardno, 2018). Figure (1) explains the key competencies used in analysis:

Figure 1. Analytical framework for the curriculum document analysis.

Source: Developed by the author.

4. Findings

The analysis was deductively based on the above conceptual framework; that is, I used the four teaching competencies relevant to international-mindedness as illustrated in Figure 1 as the basis for analysis (see Table 1 above).

Theme 1: Bringing the World into the Classroom

Generally, bringing the world issues and cultures into the classroom/teaching is missing at university level according to key university documents. For instance, the university vision focuses on pioneering in knowledge societies, whereas the mission addresses society service in an attempt to connect the university to the society. The vision reads 'Leadership in building a knowledge society' and the mission reads: "Assiut University is a public university that mobilises its energies and employs them to achieve its vision through high-quality education that produces distinguished generations of graduates, capable of innovation and competition in the labour market." (Vision of Assiut University).

As illustrated in the above statements, the focus is on issues such as quality education, university values, leadership and innovation but not integration of world issues and cultures into teaching. At faculty level, integrating world issues and cultures into the classroom is also missing and no representation/indication thereof was reflected. Only indirect indication was identified. The faculty's vision reads, 'The Faculty of Education, Assiut University, aims to be pioneer in the fields of education, learning, and scholarly research, and society service at regional and international

levels/stages' (Faculty's vision, Assiut University website, p.2). The faculty mission has thus showed no reference to integrating world issues and cultures into the classroom.

At departmental level, a similar conclusion could be drawn. By reviewing the official website of the Department of Curriculum and Teaching Methods as the provider of the ELTE for preservice EFL teachers, I found no direct connection between its vision and integrating world issues and cultures. However, some indirect reference to this teaching competency was identified. For example, the overview of the department reads: *"We offer a broad range of academic programmes where we prepare professionals for leadership roles in a variety of educational settings by sophisticated teaching methodologies and interdisciplinary coursework [...]"* (Overview of the Department of Curriculum & Teaching Methods, p.1).

The faculty provides a wide range of academic programmes that use advanced teaching techniques and interdisciplinary coursework to prepare professionals for leadership roles in a variety of educational settings. This is in line with the department's focus on developing professional competencies, particularly the capacity to lead, innovate, and use cutting-edge teaching techniques in a variety of settings. Since it gives graduates the information, abilities, and attitudes to handle challenging educational issues, this kind of leadership-oriented training is ingrained in the department's vision and is framed as a competency. Because developing capable leaders is in line with the objective of promoting educational practices that enhance societal and environmental well-being, this vision also directly relates to the department's emphasis on sustainable development.

There is, however, a focus on sustainable development as per the following statement that reads *'We present joyful learning experience and sophisticated academic programme through increasing the ability of the department to contribute to sustainable development and to serve the community and the environment'* (Overview of the Department of Curriculum and Teaching Methods). Additionally, the department goal shows no connection to integrating world issues into classrooms. The department goal reads: *'1) to develop graduates who will facilitate optimal teaching and learning for all students, and 2) to influence educational policies, practices, and outcomes'* (the Department Programmes goal). The departmental focus is on other pedagogical issues such as educational policies rather than explicitly highlighting the integration of world issues into classrooms. This conclusion is valid across the different academic levels investigated from the university to faculty and the departmental and programme levels too. The discontinuous presence of IM in university versus faculty level can be interpreted by suggesting there is absent coordination between different HE stakeholders in this context. While curriculum developers at faculty level might indirectly consider IM, university stakeholders or officials probably consider other issues rather than IM to be prioritised in their HE agenda.

Theme 2: Analysing Resources from Around the World

This competency of analysing resources from around the world is not demonstrated at university level. As illustrated in the analysis of the Assiut University mission and vision statements, the focus of the statements is not on analysing global resources to benefit the educational process across the university. Analysing global resources is also missing in the goal statement at university level with the focus being on educating a graduate capable of innovation and competition, the connection between university and society, and instilling the university values and traditions. The strategic objectives as part of the University Plan (2019-2024) includes different goals, which also establishes no connection to analysing resources from around the world. For instance, one of the items of the second objective reads: *"Supporting the connection with the global scientific society by such procedures as organising international conferences and encouraging scholarly publication in international journals"* (Item 3, Strategic Objective 2, Strategic Plan of Assiut University 2019-2024)

There is some interest in engaging globally by stressing the connection with the global scholarly community but there is, however, no indication to using any of the resources from around the world such as those reflecting different cultures and countries to support teaching across the university. Likewise, analysing global resources is missing across the different objectives of the university strategic plan. For example, objective 3 reads *"Raising awareness about environmental and social issues' and 'international cooperation to solve environmental issues/problems"* (Objective 3, University Strategic Plan). All such examples from the objectives section highlight that analysing resources from around the world contexts and cultures was not demonstrated in Assiut University Strategic Plan.

At faculty level, analysing resources from around the world is not demonstrated and no representation or indication thereof is reflected, with the focus being on pioneering in the fields of education, learning, scholarly research, and society service at regional and international levels. The faculty's mission has also showed no reference to analysing

ing global resources. At departmental level, a similar conclusion could be drawn. The Department of Curriculum and Teaching Methods website demonstrates no connection between its vision and analysing resources from around the world. Furthermore, the department goal has not demonstrated any connection to analysing global resources. This result is also evident at the programme level, with the focus being not on analysing resources from around the world but rather on emphasising the need for PSTs to be provided with content and pedagogical knowledge (CPK).

Analysing resources from around the world is also absent from the section on skills required from candidate teachers. Some skills were examined for their connection to analysing global resources, such as the need for PSTs to 'acquire the skills of studying and analysing human and social phenomena, cases, and projects' (Intellectual skills, ELTE curriculum – primary, p.10) which might indicate a reflective and analytical ability. It is worth noting that the instances identified in these documents are those that indicate cultural and other related issues. This, in turn, highlights that ELTE curriculum developers are more focused on local than international-mindedness.

Theme 3: Critically Examining Your Culture

Generally, there is a noticeable focus on the domestic cultural context and a confirmation that a preservice teacher should recognise and maintain the domestic/national culture rather than any mention of examination of such culture. For instance, in the English language teacher education (ELTE) curriculum description of the graduate PST profile, this confirmation on domestic cultural identity is crystalised. The item reads: 'The graduate should recognise the basic cultural identity of the nation' (Item 12, the graduate PST profile, ELTE curriculum – primary, p.6). This focus on the domestic context is also highlighted in the graduate PST profile as in the following statement: 'The graduate should participate in nurturing/development of national belonging values, democracy, tolerance, and acceptance of others' (Item 13, curriculum objectives, ELTE curriculum – primary, p.9). This item is a bit complex: on the one hand, it stresses the local-mindedness/orientation by asserting the need for graduate teachers to nurture the national values but it also broadens the graduates' perspectives by highlighting the need to nurture other IM-related values such as tolerance and acceptance of others.

Furthermore, sections of the TEFL teacher education curriculum examined for their connection to intercultural competence are the same as those sections examined above including the mission, vision, and preservice teachers' profile including their knowledge and different skillsets. For instance, the mission statement reads: "The faculty is an accredited institution that educates a creative teacher who can keep pace with technological advancements and modern approaches in education (teaching) and learning ..." (the Faculty of Education mission, p.1).

The mission of the ELTE curriculum focuses on preparing creative teachers, emphasising awareness of technological advancements, but it overlooks international-mindedness (IM). The only connection to culture in the curriculum objectives is related to developing cultural awareness by introducing preservice teachers to the civilisations of the English-speaking world, aiming for understanding and interaction with those peoples (Item 3, ELTE curriculum – primary, p.9). This focus is limited to the culture of native English speakers, rather than a broader global cultural perspective. Additionally, other objectives prioritise maintaining domestic cultural identity over examining one's own culture, indicating that the curriculum is more focused on developing national cultural competence than intercultural competence. This reflects a local rather than global cultural orientation in the current ELTE curriculum for primary teachers.

Theme 4: Reflecting on school systems and peculiarities

Likewise, there is no reference to this theme in the teacher education documents analysed. However, some indication is made to global systems of education and the need for preservice teachers to be aware of them, yet without explicitly stating that PSTs should reflect on such systems. For instance, the ELTE curriculum mission statement reads: "The preparation of a creative teacher who is capable of competition in labour market using technological advancements and contemporary trends of education and learning, and who is qualified to excel in scholarship to develop his/her society." (Mission statement, ELTE curriculum – secondary, p.5).

The statement does not make any direct connection to intercultural competence by indicating the education of teachers who can either examine their culture to improve teaching or reflect on educational systems worldwide. Furthermore, the reference to educating and preparing teachers who can compete using contemporary trends in education does not directly reflect teachers' engagement with global educational systems using reflection on their practices.

Worth noting is that this competency of reflecting on educational systems received some little attention, though indirect, in the ELTE curriculum (for secondary teachers) which indicates that preservice teachers' engagement with international educational systems is somewhat important for curriculum developers. For instance, in the mental skills section of the skillsets preservice teachers require in their career, the following objective reads: *'The teacher should be able to recognise educational policies and systems'* (Item 2/4, mental objectives, ELTE curriculum for secondary teachers, p.13). However, only the objective clarifies that teachers should be aware of such systems without outlining how or who should facilitate doing so or even illustrating the type of engagement with systems beyond recognition thereof. A similar objective to item 2/4 was reiterated in the mental sections of the skill sets required from teachers in ELTE curriculum for primary teachers. Only the choice of words (verbs) differs, so instead of *'the teacher should recognise ...'*, the objective reads: *'the teacher should understand educational policies and systems'* (Mental skills, ELTE curriculum – primary, p.17). Other than that, very scant connection could be established between the objectives and any other section of both the ELTE curricula for primary and/or secondary teachers. This highlights the absence of intercultural competence as a component considered by ELTE curriculum developers.

Some references to engagement in the documents focus on local rather than global contexts. For example, the ELTE Curriculum vision for Secondary School Teachers states: *"Educating an excellent teacher who can keep pace with progress at the local and regional levels ..."* (ELTE Curriculum vision, p.5). This regional focus perhaps pertains to the Arab context surrounding Egypt, without referencing the wider international context. Similarly, the graduate profile emphasises local issues, stating: *"The graduate should participate in solving professional and societal problems using scientific methods"* (Item 15, ELTE curriculum for primary teachers, p.6). Cultural integration appears only in the curriculum objectives, with one item stating: *"The ELTE curriculum for primary teachers aims to develop the PSTs' cultural awareness by familiarising them with the civilisations and cultures of the English language speaking peoples, and interacting with these peoples"* (Item 3, curriculum objectives, ELTE curriculum for primary teachers, p.9).

5. Discussion

The findings demonstrate that the EFL teacher education curriculum is largely focused on local issues and lacks an international perspective. However, IM can enhance education by encouraging receptivity to the world and its varied resources, resulting in a globally-focused learning environment where students flourish. Reflective teaching and other active pedagogies can help realise this potential. At the moment, IM is not present in any of the four competencies shown in Figure 1. The Egyptian curriculum is still locally focused, despite the fact that both national and international actors influence educational reform (Ginsburg & Megahed, 2008). According to El-Halawany (2018), it is out of date and relies more on passive pedagogies and rote memorisation than on practical skills. On the other hand, studies highlight the importance of incorporating instant messaging (IM) into teacher education (e.g., Davis & Kelly, 2020; Lee, 2018; Smith, 2017), and Baily and Holmarsdottir (2019) associate it with innovation. Universities must accept the responsibility that teachers must have the skills, knowledge, and dispositions necessary for global engagement in light of the growing diversity of their student bodies (Papanikolaou et al., 2020).

A prominent feature in the Egyptian higher/teacher education documents is local-mindedness with the four competencies being not explicitly addressed. There seems to be a discrepancy between such local orientations and those in the international agenda in HE. Locally, international-mindedness is absent in the Egyptian HE context across different levels with the focus rather being on equipping preservice teachers with subject matter competencies or CPK and skills such as lesson planning and use of technology. The four competencies constructing the conceptual framework of this study are not addressed in the Egyptian TE documents, which is a departure from literature emphasising the need to integrate them in teaching (e.g., Hongboontri & Keawkhong, 2014; Kerkhoff & Cloud, 2020; Kim et al, 2023; Eden et al, 2023; Nopas & Kerdsoomboon, 2024). Therefore, this can shift the attention of researchers in international education, and mainly those exploring international-mindedness, to consider investigating IM in contexts that are less explored such as the Egyptian context.

A potential reason for such local-mindedness in the Egyptian TE context is perhaps the premise that teacher educators cater towards a local marketplace, and thus curriculum developers do not cater to integrate global and/or intercultural competencies in the process of teacher education. According to Assaad et al (2018), there is a substantial mismatch between the outputs of HE system and labour market needs, with the public sector being the dominant or major employer in Egypt. Thus, I argue that despite the government rhetoric for more internationalisation, there appears to be limited scope of this within the initial teacher education (ITT), particularly for English teachers. I also sug-

gest that it is perhaps beneficial to integrate IM in the ITT curriculum/process to increase teachers' employability in both national and international educational markets.

Additionally, this study furthers the discussions about decolonising the process of internationalisation in HE. The majority of the literature is based on organisations in powerful geopolitical contexts like the United States and the United Kingdom, where internationalisation is frequently framed by powerful, well-funded models. This research reveals a distinct set of dynamics by looking at an institution in the Global South, where internationalisation interacts with regional cultural imperatives, resource limitations, and local socioeconomic priorities. This viewpoint calls for more research into how international educational agendas are negotiated outside of established power centres and emphasises the need to reframe internationalisation as a varied, contextually embedded process rather than a uniform model.

This study makes a contribution to the field of HE in the following ways. First, it contributes to the theory and practice of international education by showing the tensions around IM as a fluid complex concept. These tensions might include differences between local and international priorities; for example, local contexts may prioritise developing teachers' national awareness and strengthen their local culture whereas IM calls for openness to different world cultures. This way, I suggest that a contextualised approach to implementing IM in the teacher education curriculum can adopt a glocalised approach which means considering international cultures while prioritising local-context aims and conditions.

Second, this study also contributes to educational practice in introducing international-mindedness in the Egyptian context given that the results show that it is a locally minded context with the focus being on local educational labour market without highlighting the need to prepare/educate teachers capable of competing at a global scale (Amer, 2007). Egypt is thriving as a hub for education and HE in the Arab World and the Middle East region (MENA), and it has made some significant leaps in internationalisation endeavours, as exemplified by a surge in many HEIs seeking (international) accreditation. Thus, the introduction of international-mindedness could be one way to reemphasise its stance in the context of internationalisation. Thus, teachers could be more employable given that they will acquire the knowledge bases, attitudes, and skillsets required in international and multicultural contexts, and this could be viewed economically as an additive value.

Moreover, the study makes a theoretical contribution to the field of English language teaching in the Egyptian context as it takes the lead for investigating IM in the teacher education context, an area that still needs further investigation and scholarly attention. Perhaps English language teachers in the Egyptian context are among the most teachers who often seek travel opportunities. In other words, many of them opt for academic and professional mobility to seek professional and financial development (Ghoneim & Elghotmy, 2016). This way, the study fills a gap in the literature regarding the internationalisation of (English language) teacher education in Egypt while focusing on and utilising international-mindedness as a conceptual framework for TE curriculum development/improvement. This is an area where, to the best of my knowledge, scant literature adopts an international lens towards teacher education in the Egyptian context with the focus being on developing other subject matter competencies teachers need.

The applicability of the conceptual framework can also be extended beyond the subject or major of EFL teacher education to perhaps include other fields such as STEM teacher education since the framework is originally designed/developed by the researcher to be universal rather than discipline-specific. The study also suggests that the gap in practice could be fulfilled by embedding IM in the TE curriculum using the current conceptual framework as a guiding framework for a new set of competencies teachers could acquire. That is why the current study calls for more scholarly attention to be paid towards internationalisation in teacher education in less explored contexts as the Egyptian TE context. Doing so, arguably, myriad opportunities could be provided for preservice and in-service teachers for employability in the global marketplace.

6. Conclusion and implications

International-mindedness was generally absent in the Egyptian teacher education curriculum documents at all levels—university, faculty, department, and programme. The ELTE curriculum primarily focused on equipping preservice teachers with competencies related to subject matter (content knowledge) and pedagogical skills, such as lesson planning and use of technology. Nevertheless, some indirect references to international-mindedness were identified, particularly in the mission, vision, and objectives of the faculty and ELTE programme. These references suggested a poor connection between the curriculum and international-mindedness competencies.

The curriculum developers' mindset seems to be focused on the domestic educational landscape in the Egyptian HE context, as evidenced by the emphasis on serving the local community. This suggests that the curriculum is not addressing international dimensions of teacher education particularly from an internationally-minded lens. One implication is that ELTE curriculum developers should incorporate international and multicultural aspects, such as knowledge, skills, and attitudes for global engagement and intercultural competence (see Figure 1). This incorporation should not be limited to a particular subject area such as EFL teacher education as it can be extended to other fields as well such as STEM teacher education. Another implication is that preservice teachers should be given opportunities for developing international-mindedness via instructional and training experiences, such as cross-cultural and intercultural communication partnerships and projects.

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